

Evaluation of Cephalometric Norms for COGS Analysis in Bhopal Population

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ABSTRACT

Cephalometrics for Orthognathic Surgery (COGS) parameters of hard and soft tissue of one state population in India cannot be applied to another group. So, it becomes necessary to understand the cephalometric norms in populations of different state. The aim of the study was to determine the hard tissue cephalometric norms for orthodontic sequency applicable to the population of Madhya Pradesh using HP plane as reference plane. The study was conducted in Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics, Mansarovar Dental College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bhopal. The present analysis was made on lateral cephalograms. Horizontal Plane (HP) is used as base line for comparison of most of the data in this analysis. The cephalometric norms for orthognathic surgery were done on 130 Class I patients. The mean values for the COGS analysis was significantly different from the normal. There were significant difference in the COGS value for both males and females. These values were recommended for use in the orthognathic surgery done on the central Indian population. The cephalometric norms for orthognathic surgery found in the study done on central Indian population were significantly different than the norm of the Caucasian population. The norms for the Indian population are taken into account during orthognathic treatment planning.

KEY WORDS: orthogenetic surgery, cephalometric norms, burrstone analysis

INTRODUCTION:

Facial harmony and balance are maintained by the facial skeleton and its overlying soft tissue. Orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning are based on the evaluation of the patient's soft tissue profile^[1]. Lateral cephalometric radiograph is an extremely useful diagnostic tool in orthodontic practice. It was introduced in 1931 by Broadbent Cephalometrics. It is the most commonly used clinical tool for evaluating jaw relationships in all the three planes that is sagittal, transverse and vertical planes. In modern day practice, the treatment goal for any patient that requires combined orthodontic treatment and orthognathic surgery are determined systematically through cephalometrics, the importance of which can be elaborated as follows: 1.

Cephalometric analysis aid in diagnosis of skeletal and dental problems; 2. It can help simulate orthognathic surgery through 'Surgical Treatment Objective' (STO) and 3. It allows the clinician to evaluate the changes following the completion of the treatment.

At present, a large number of adults-seeking orthodontic treatment require orthognathic surgery. For successful treatment of orthognathic surgery, accurate diagnosis of facial, skeletal, and dental problems is a must. For this reason, a specialized cephalometric appraisal system called Cephalometrics for Orthognathic Surgery analysis (COGS) concerning the hard tissue and soft tissue of the face had been developed by Burstone et al^[2].

Cephalometrics for Orthognathic Surgery (COGS) was developed at University of Connecticut in 1978. It has the characteristics which makes it particularly adaptable for the evaluation of surgical orthognathic problems.

The COGS system describes the horizontal and vertical position of facial bones by use of a constant coordinate system that includes various linear and angular measurements which are measured

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either parallel or perpendicular to true horizontal plane (HP). This HP can correct arbitrary nature of reference planes (SN and FH) used in other analysis that also vary just as the landmarks in maxilla and mandible that are related to them. Another advantage offered by this analysis is that it is based on the landmarks that can be altered by various surgical procedures. Various rectilinear measurements describe the discrepancy in critical skeletal components that can be readily transferred to acetate overlay and study casts for detailed planning of treatment and post surgical evaluation.

The values of COGS analysis proved to be very useful as they are based largely on rectilinear measurements that can be used during surgery for prediction overlays, mock surgery, and may serve as a basis for the assessment of post-treatment stability. These analyses have been extensively used for research studie^[3].

However, all these studies were carried out in Caucasians based on sample populations of European-American ancestries whose reference value may not be applicable to other ethnic types. For this reason, attempts have been made to investigate the differences of the human face among various ethnic groups including Africans^[4] African-Americans^[4] Chinese^[5] oreans^[6] Saudi Arabians^[7] Mexican-Americans^[8] Puerto Ricans^[9].

The skeletal, dental, as well as soft tissue variations exist in different groups of population. India is a large country with around 15 % of the world population. The cephalometric parameters of hard and soft tissue of one state population cannot be applied to another group. So, it becomes necessary to understand the cephalometric norms for different populations. Thus, the present study was conducted to determine the norms of cephalometrics for orthognathic surgery (COGS) in the population of Bhopal (MP).

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The present cross-sectional study was conducted in Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics of Mansarovar Dental College, Bhopal.

Study Population:

The study population comprised of patients having age group of 18 - 40 years having Class I molar relationship with aesthically pleasant profile not gone for any orthodontic treatment previously.

Approval from Authorities : The study protocol had got approval from Institutional Ethical Committee of Mansarovar Dental College, Bhopal.

Training and Calibration of Examiner: A single examiner performed all the examinations throughout the study. The investigator was trained and calibrated in the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics in order to minimize the diagnostic variability.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients between 18 to 40 years of age; Well balanced and aesthetically pleasing facial profile; Class-I molar and canine relation, normal overjet and overbite with midline coinciding; No history of orthodontic, orthognathic or plastic surgery treatment.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below 18 years of age; Patients having Class II and Class III Profile; Patients having previous history of Orthodontic or Orthognathic treatment; Patients having asymmetry of face; Patients not willing to give consent for study.

Implementing the Survey: The survey was systematically scheduled to spread over a period of 6 months from August 2017 to August 2018. The team, with a postgraduate students and a intern screened the patient reporting the OPD. Written Informed consent was obtained from the study subjects before examination. The examination of the subjects were examined seated on the dental chair. The examination was done with the single examiner so as to remove the inter examiner variability. The present analysis was made on lateral cephalograms. The base line used for comparison of most of the data in this analysis is a constructed plane called as Horizontal Plane (HP). It is constructed by drawing a line 7^0 from SN, intersecting at N point. The reference plane used in the study was arbitrary and was constructed assuming SN plane is normal (Figure 1).

From the digitized points, six angular and 17 linear measurements were obtained and divided into 5 Groups. Cranial base (Figure 2):

1. Posterior cranial base (AR-PTM) mm: a distance from AR to PTM, parallel to HP.
2. Anterior cranial base (PTM-N) mm: a distance from PTM to N, parallel to HP.

Horizontal skeletal relationship (Figure 2):

1. Facial convexity (N-A-PG): an angle formed by the line N-A and the line A-pG.
2. Maxillary protrusion (N-A) mm: a distance from point A to perpendicular line from N, parallel to HP.
3. Mandibular protrusion (N-B) mm: a distance from point B to perpendicular line from N, parallel to HP.

Figure 1: Cephalometric Diagram showing HP Plane.

- | | |
|---------------------------------|------------------------------|
| 11. MP – HP (angle) | 17. Ar – Go (linear) |
| 12. U1 – NF (\perp NF) | 18. B – Pg (\parallel MP) |
| 13. L1 – MP (\perp MP) | 19. Ar – Go – Gn (angle) |
| 14. U6 – NF (\perp NF) | 20. OP – HP (angle) |
| 15. L6 – MP (\perp MP) | 21. U1 – NF (angle) |
| 16. PNS – ANS (\parallel HP) | 22. L1 – MP (angle) |

Figure 3: Hard Tissue Cephalometric Analysis.

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|-------------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Ar – PTM (\parallel HP) | 5. N – Pg (\parallel HP) |
| 2. PTM – N (\parallel HP) | 6. N – ANS (\perp HP) |
| 3. N – A – Pg (angle) | 7. ANS – Gn (\perp HP) |
| 4. N – A (\parallel HP) | 8. PNS – N (\perp HP) |

Figure 2: Hard Tissue Cephalometric Analysis.

4. Chin protrusion (N–PG) mm: a distance from pogonion to a perpendicular line from N, parallel to HP.

Vertical skeletal relationship (Figure 2 & Figure 3):

1. Upper anterior facial height (N–ANS) mm: a distance from N to ANS, perpendicular to HP.
2. Lower anterior facial height (ANS–GN) mm: a distance from ANS to GN, perpendicular to HP.
3. Upper posterior facial height (PNS–N) mm: a perpendicular distance from HP to PNS.
4. Mandibular plane angle (MP–HP): an angle formed between GO–GN line and HP.

Vertical dental relationship (Figure 3):

1. Upper anterior dental height (U1–NF) mm: a perpendicular line from the incisal edge of upper incisor to NF.
2. Lower anterior dental height (L1–MP) mm: a perpendicular line from the incisal edge of lower incisor to MP.
3. Upper posterior dental height (UMT–NF) mm: a perpendicular line from the mesiobuccal cusp tip of upper first molar to NF.
4. Lower posterior dental height (LMT–MP) mm: a

Table 1: Comparison of COGS Analysis on the basis of gender using Burststone Analysis

Measurements	BURSTONE ANALYSIS			
	Female	Male	t value	p value
Cranial Base				
Ar – Ptm (mm)	35.90 ± 3.1	38.56 ± 3.4	2.06	0.02*
Ptm – N(mm)	51.74 ± 4.8	55.74 ± 5.9	2.11	0.03*
Horizontal (Skeletal)				
N-A-Pg (Deg)	5.12 ± 5.3	5.40 ± 6.25	0.65	0.59
N-A(mm)	2.58 ± 3.28	0.98 ± 1.38	3.06	0.01*
N-B(mm)	-1.40 ± 2.82	-3.00 ± 3.2	9.68	0.01*
N-Pg (mm)	-2.4 ± 4.84	0.81 ± 2.7	4.39	0.01*
Vertical (skeletal)				
N-ANS(mm)	52.6 ± 3.09	54.8 ± 3.6	1.42	0.11
ANS-GN(mm)	64.46 ± 4.82	69.56 ± 4.3	2.38	0.03*
PNS-N(mm)	47.67 ± 1.70	55.79 ± 3.4	15.34	0.01*
MP-HP (Deg)	25.02 ± 6.45	20.46 ± 6.2	5.58	0.01*
Vertical (Dental)				
U1-NF(mm)	28.41 ± 3.08	30.81 ± 2.6	1.99	0.04*
U6-NF(mm)	23.84 ± 2.58	25.55 ± 2.9	2.49	0.03*
L1-MP(mm)	39.94 ± 5.93	44.23 ± 3.7	4.23	0.01*
L6-MP(mm)	32.37 ± 2.64	36.51 ± 2.9	3.19	0.01*
Maxilla and Mandible				
PNS – ANS(mm)	52.47 ± 3.40	54.25 ± 2.8	1.59	0.12
Ar-Go (mm)	45.80 ± 4.39	53.19 ± 4.9	6.09	0.01*
Go-Pg (mm)	74.85 ± 5.04	82.75 ± 5.4	4.58	0.01*
B-Pg (mm)	5.84 ± 1.85	8.75 ± 1.9	12.29	0.01*
Ar-Go-Gn (Deg)	122.10 ± 4.84	122.45 ± 7.9	0.21	0.90
Dental				
OP-HP (Deg)	6.85 ± 5.10	9.45 ± 5.9	4.85	0.01*
A-B(mm)	3.67 ± 2.79	2.58 ± 3.5	2.74	0.03*
U1-NF(Deg)	113.12 ± 5.99	115.82 ± 4.9	1.94	0.07
L1-MP(Deg)	99.86 ± 6.42	98.24 ± 6.3	1.25	0.29

* Significant, Student T test

perpendicular line from the mesiobuccal cusp tip of lower first molar to MP.

Maxilla and mandible (Figure 3):

1. Maxillary length (PNS–ANS) mm: a distance from PNS to ANS, parallel to HP.
2. Mandibular ramus length (AR–GO) mm: a line from AR to GO.
3. Mandibular body length (GO–PG) mm: a distance from GO to PG.
4. Chin depth (B–PG) mm: a distance from B point to a perpendicular line to MP through PG.
5. Gonial angle (AR–GO–GN): an angle between ramal length and MP.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The data was transformed from pre-coded survey form to computer. The job of data entry, comparison of the study population was done by using student t test with the help of statistical package of social sciences (SPSS version 22.0). The level of statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS:

The mean Cephalometric norms that had been found in Bhopal (Central India) population using HP plane (Burststone Analysis) was divided in 5 parts. Various angular and linear measurements for both hard and soft tissues among males and females

Table 2: Comparison of norms between the study and Caucasian males.

Measurements	Male			
	Male	Standard	t value	p value
Cranial Base				
Ar – Ptm (mm)	38.56 - 3.4	37.1 - 2.8	0.45	0.09
Ptm – N(mm)	55.74 - 5.9	52.8 - 4.1	2.24	0.03*
Horizontal (Skeletal)				
N-A-Pg (Deg)	5.40 - 6.25	3.9 - 6.4	2.89	0.02*
N-A(mm)	0.98 - 1.38	0 - 3.7	1.04	0.45
N-B(mm)	-3.00 - 3.2	-5.3 - 6.7	3.59	0.01*
N-Pg (mm)	0.81 - 2.7	-4.3 - 8.5	3.69	0.01*
Vertical (skeletal)				
N-ANS(mm)	54.8 - 3.6	54 - 3.2	0.74	0.45
ANS-GN(mm)	69.56 - 4.3	68.6 - 3.8	0.89	0.31
PNS-N(mm)	55.79 - 3.4	53.89 - 2.9	1.69	0.11
MP-HP (Deg)	20.46 - 6.2	24.0 - 5.0	2.47	0.03*
Vertical (Dental)				
U1-NF(mm)	30.81 - 2.6	30.5 - 2.1	0.15	0.85
U6-NF(mm)	25.55 - 2.9	26.2 - 2.1	0.89	0.27
L1-MP(mm)	44.23 - 3.7	45.0 - 2.1	0.55	0.66
L6-MP(mm)	36.51 - 2.9	35.8 - 2.6	1.14	0.17
Maxilla and Mandible				
PNS – ANS(mm)	54.25 - 2.8	57.5 - 2.5	1.59	0.12
Ar-Go (mm)	53.19 - 4.9	52.0 - 4.2	6.09	0.01*
Go-Pg (mm)	82.75 - 5.4	83.7 - 4.6	4.58	0.01*
B-Pg (mm)	8.75 - 1.9	8.9 - 1.7	12.29	0.01*
Ar-Go-Gn(Deg)	122.45 - 7.9	119.0 - 6.85	0.21	0.90
Dental				
OP-HP (Deg)	9.45 - 5.9	6.1 - 5.1	4.85	0.01*
A-B(mm)	2.58 - 3.5	-1.1 - 2.0	3.74	0.01*
U1-NF(Deg)	115.82 - 4.9	111 - 4.7	2.65	0.03*
L1-MP(Deg)	98.24 - 6.3	95.9 - 5.7	2.89	0.03*

* Significant, Student T test

are tabulated. All readings obtained were subjected to statistical analysis for calculating mean and standard deviation (SD).

The standard values between males and females were compared with the help of student t test. The values show significant differences between

males and females in most of the parameters (Table 1).

The values are compared with Caucasian population by using unpaired t test. The Cephalometric norms for males show significant difference between study population and Caucasian population (Table 2). The Cephalometric norms for females also show significant difference between

Table 3: Comparison of norms between the study and Caucasian Females.

Measurements	Female			
	Female	Standard	t value	p value
Cranial Base				
Ar – Ptm (mm)	35.90 ± 3.1	32.8 ± 1.9	2.15	0.04*
Ptm – N(mm)	51.74 ± 4.8	50.9 ± 3.0	2.24	0.03*
Horizontal (Skeletal)				
N-A-Pg (Deg)	5.12 ± 5.3	2.6 ± 5.1	2.89	0.02*
N-A(mm)	2.58 ± 3.28	-2 ± 3.7	1.04	0.45
N-B(mm)	-1.40 ± 2.82	-6.9 ± 4.3	3.59	0.01*
N-Pg (mm)	-2.4 ± 4.84	-6.5 ± 5.1	3.69	0.01*
Vertical (skeletal)				
N-ANS(mm)	52.6 ± 3.09	54 ± 3.2	0.74	0.45
ANS-GN(mm)	64.46 ± 4.82	61.3 ± 3.3	0.89	0.31
PNS-N(mm)	47.67 ± 1.70	50.6 ± 2.2	1.69	0.11
MP-HP (Deg)	25.02 ± 6.45	23.0 ± 5.0	2.47	0.03*
Vertical (Dental)				
U1-NF(mm)	28.41 ± 3.08	27.5 ± 1.7	0.15	0.85
U6-NF(mm)	23.84 ± 2.58	23.0 ± 1.3	0.89	0.27
L1-MP(mm)	39.94 ± 5.93	40.8 ± 1.8	0.55	0.66
L6-MP(mm)	32.37 ± 2.64	32.0 ± 1.9	1.14	0.17
Maxilla and Mandible				
PNS – ANS(mm)	52.47 ± 3.40	52.6 ± 3.5	1.59	0.12
Ar-Go (mm)	45.80 ± 4.39	46.8 ± 2.5	6.09	0.01*
Go-Pg (mm)	74.85 ± 5.04	74.3 ± 5.8	4.58	0.01*
B-Pg (mm)	5.84 ± 1.85	7.2 ± 1.9	12.29	0.01*
Ar-Go-Gn (Deg)	122.10 ± 4.84	122.0 ± 6.9	0.21	0.90
Dental				
OP-HP (Deg)	6.85 ± 5.10	7.1 ± 2.5	4.85	0.01*
A-B(mm)	3.67 ± 2.79	-0.4 ± 2.5	3.74	0.01*
U1-NF(Deg)	113.12 ± 5.99	112 ± 5.3	2.65	0.03*
L1-MP(Deg)	99.86 ± 6.42	95.9 ± 5.7	2.89	0.03*

* Significant, Student t test

study population and Caucasian population (Table 3).

DISCUSSION:

The attainment of facial proportionality is one of the principal goals in the treatment of dentofacial deformities and can be achieved with properly planned and executed orthognathic surgical techniques. The goal of maxillofacial surgery is to treat any jaw imbalance and the resulting incorrect bite, which could adversely affect the cosmetic (esthetic) appearance as well as the proper functioning of the teeth.

Most of the cephalometric analyses^[10,11] which are used today in India have originated in White North American adults. The cephalometric norms of one

ethnic group need not necessarily apply to another ethnic group because of noticeable variation of the craniofacial morphology in different ethnic groups.

Previous studies have established specific cephalometric norms with different ethnic backgrounds, showing different facial features^[10-13].

The racial, facial, and skeletal characteristics of the patient play a critical role in orthognathic surgery planning. Therefore, existence of such database becomes an absolute necessity for carrying out these surgical procedures.

Over the centuries, India has received large groups of people of different ethnical and cultural origins. This has lead to dispersion of different ethnic groups in the Indian population. People living in North

India have different facial form than people living in South India.

This study was done for the purpose of establishing the cephalometric norms for population of Central India population and also to establish the individual cephalometric norms of males and females. It focused on 200 males and 200 females of Madhya Pradesh origin having a class I occlusion and well-balanced faces. The young adults were examined with age range of 18–25 years.

The COGS analysis revealed that males had increased anterior cranial base length and females had increased middle and lower third facial height, anterior divergence of mandible, in both the analysis which is in agreement to the study conducted by Trivedi K et al^[10] on Rajasthan, Mohode et al on Marathi population but contrast to the study done by Grewal et al^[12] on Indo-Aryans who have vertically growing mandible.

The study had found the significant differences among the most of the parameters as compared to the different Indian population used for comparison i.e. East Indian population by Sahoo N et al^[14], Rajasthan Population by Trivedi et al^[10], Karnataka Population by Arunkumar K. V. et al^[15], North Indian Population by Tikku T et al^[16] which shows the significant difference in facial form among the Indian population.

CONCLUSION:

Cephalometric norms were established by using HP Plane for the patient who requires maxillofacial surgery was developed by to use landmarks and measurements that can be altered by common surgical procedures.

The cephalometric norms obtained from the study were significantly different from the measurement of the Caucasian population done by Burstone and the studies conducted on different population. Therefore, it can be used with confidence for COGS Analysis in patients requiring surgical management among Central Indian Population.

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